

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17139298

Effects Of Health Instructions On Knowledge Of Anaemia Among Women Attending Antenatal Clinics In Tertiary Hospitals In Delta State, Nigeria

IGBI, Bright Jessah, OGBE, J. O. & NWACHUKWU, A. E.

**Department of Health and Safety Education,
Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effects of health instruction on knowledge of anaemia among women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State, Nigeria. The study adopted a quasi-experimental design of a pre and post-tests. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from respondents, Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data. Three (3) research questions and three (3) null hypotheses guided and formulated for the study respectively. Findings revealed that women in both experimental and control groups had low knowledge of anaemia prior to the administration of health instructions as an intervention. The pretest results indicated widespread low health knowledge of anaemia as one of the pregnancy-related ailments. However, after the administration of health instructions, the experimental group demonstrated significant improvement in their knowledge of the causes, effects, and prevention of anaemia. In contrast, the control group showed no significant improvement. The results confirmed that the intervention (health instructions) was an effective tool for improvement of the knowledge of anaemia especially during pregnancy thereby preventing maternal and child mortality caused by this ailment among pregnant women. Based on these findings, the study recommended among others that health instructions should be integrated into routine antenatal care where health educators and antenatal care providers regularly deliver structured health instructions to enhance women's knowledge of anaemia especially its causes and effects on pregnancy and measures for its prevention in order to reduce incidences of pregnancy complications and maternal deaths caused by it. It also recommended that Government and health administrators should ensure that health educators are fully engaged in the healthcare sector to ensure that they collaborate with doctors and nurses to provide accurate health knowledge of the preventive measures against anaemia.

Keywords: Health instruction, Anaemia, pregnancy-related ailments, health knowledge, antenatal clinics

INTRODUCTION

Health instruction is a fundamental aspect of health education processes that uses a more focused procedure in disseminating specific health-related knowledge aimed at prevention of diseases, safety of lives and promotion of health of individuals and communities. Ilo (2017) explained that health instruction is a planned form of interaction whereby health topics intended to improve health knowledge, attitude and practice are taught in order to equip individuals with relevant health information capable of influencing their health behaviours positively. Robinson (2023) stated health instruction focuses on impartation of knowledge to individuals on specific health topics or issues in order to improve their health knowledge on such health topics and at the same time prevent ignorance about that given health issue.

Ignorance about several health issues, particularly maternal death seems to be increasing among women everyday given the alarming rates of maternal mortality arising from pregnancy related ailments including anaemia. UNICEF (2023) reported that in the year 2020 alone, 287,000 pregnant women lost their lives, at the rate of 800 women dying each day or one (1) woman dying between the intervals of two (2) minutes as a result of pregnancy-related ailments and childbirth issues. Among the serious pregnancy-related ailments facing pregnancy and childbirth is anaemia.

Anaemia is one of the critical pregnancy-related ailments that contribute to pregnancy complications and maternal mortalities all over the world, including Nigeria, and it appears the disease is a critical problem of public health concern that particularly affects pregnant women as well as young children globally. WHO (2023) described anaemia as a health condition that affect red blood cells thereby making the haemoglobin concentration to be lower than normal. According to WHO cited in Omote et al (2020), prevalence of anaemia in pregnancy varies, and it ranged from about 53.8% to 90.2 % in developing countries and 8.3% to 23% in developed countries. In addition, Omote et al (2020) asserted that anaemia remains one of the debilitating pregnancy-related ailments in Nigeria. Anaemia in pregnancy affect about half of all pregnant women across the globe, hence it remains a critical reproductive health challenge among pregnant women. Anaemia is an ailment that has its causative factor strongly rooted in dietary imbalance. Asrie (2017) stated that anaemia is highly regarded as one of the commonest nutritional deficiency that affects the global population to the tune of 1.6 billion people. It was also reported that out of the 1.6 billion people ravaged by cases of anaemia, 56 million of them are pregnant women (Onoh et al, 2015). Koyuncu et al (2017) citing Centre for Disease Control and Prevention, submitted that when the haemoglobin level is less than 11g/DL which is a haematocrit below 33%, it is referred to as anaemia in pregnancy. It is recommended that pregnant women should possess haemoglobin of 12-16g/DL because any haematocrit value below 12g/DL is seen as susceptibility to iron deficiency, and if it is lesser than 10.5g/DL it is highly considered as anaemia (Kadry et al, 2018). They stated further that one of the critical health problems that pregnant women could experience is anaemia and iron deficiency which predisposes them to a risk factor for preterm delivery or delivery of premature infants, low birth weight babies, difficulty in labor (inability to push during labor), shortness of breath (Dyspnea) among others. Hence, health education intervention to provide health knowledge on the causes, effects and prevention of anaemia was considered necessary in order to salvage women from pregnancy complications and maternal deaths.

Knowledge of anaemia for pregnant women ought to be constantly given through a properly planned and implemented health instruction programme. Estmat et al (2018) advocated that the most effective step aimed at reducing prevalence of anaemia in pregnancy is health education which can create much awareness about iron deficiency anaemia considering areas such as preventing the risk factors by way of iron supplementation through healthcare services and imbibing essential nutritional ingredients.

Appiah et al (2020) conducted another study in Jabuso districts in northern-western region of Ghana revealed that on the aggregate, 86.5% had low knowledge of anaemia, while 13.5% had high knowledge of anaemia, concluding that it was the lack of knowledge of anaemia made them lacked adherence to preventive measures of anaemia in pregnancy. The conclusion of this study in Ghana further reemphasized the need for health education to improve health knowledge of pregnant women in Nigeria in order to remove ignorance about the causes, effects and prevention of this pregnancy-related ailment-anaemia. In line with recommendation of Suryanarayana et al (2017) that structured health education would be effective in reducing ignorance and improve adherence to preventive measures like iron-rich diets and supplementation. Health education is a discipline with a curricular mandate to disseminate accurate health knowledge to change individuals' behaviour in health practice. In a study in Saudi-Arabia, Elsharkawy et al (2022) reported that group of persons administered with an intervention tagged Health Information Package Programme (HIPP) attained significant increase in the mean knowledge scores, food selection ability scores and improvement in their haemoglobin levels after three (3) months of the HIPP intervention to improve knowledge of anaemia among pregnant women. Hence, the study of the effects of health instructions on knowledge of the causes, effects and prevention of anaemia in pregnancy, towards

prevention of maternal death among women in Nigeria including Delta state. In consideration of this health problem posing grave health risk to pregnant women, this study was deemed necessary towards finding solutions through health education intervention, especially in the light of ignorance among pregnant women and their families on the causes, effects and prevention of anaemia. On this premise, this study was conducted to find out the effects of health instruction on knowledge of anaemia among women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State. The study focused on the application of health instructions as a health education intervention by adopting a pre and post-tests to determine the effects of four (4) weeks health instructions on improving the knowledge of the causes, effects and prevention of anaemia among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The rising cases of maternal and infant mortality in Nigeria, including Delta state is worrisome. Maternal and infant morbidity and mortalities as well as several other common pregnancy complications such as preterm delivery or delivery of premature infants, low birth weight babies, difficulty in labor (inability to push during), shortness of breath (dyspnea) are maternal health challenges associated with anaemia in pregnancy. Good number of women of reproductive age especially pregnant women are not knowledgeable of this pregnancy-related ailments thus ignorantly accuse witches and wizards as being responsible for the occurrences of many pregnancy complications and its consequential deaths among pregnant women. The persistent accusation of witchcraft being responsible for occurrences of maternal mortalities and other associated pregnancy complications among pregnant women is highly attributed to ignorance of the causes of pregnancy-related ailment such as anaemia. The witchcraft's accusation due to ignorance tends to divert attention from seeking solution through proper healthcare delivery systems.

Arising from these scenarios, it is evidenced that there is a shortfall in health knowledge of anaemia among pregnant women in Nigeria, including Delta State. Pregnant women suffer pains and preventable deaths due to the shortfall in knowledge of anaemia. Therefore, the need to experiment through the use of health instructions as a health education intervention to improve pregnant women's knowledge of anaemia necessitated this study. It was considered necessary that knowledge of this pregnancy-related ailment and its associated negative effects on pregnancy and childbirth is required among all women of reproductive age, especially pregnant women. It was hypothetically believed that good and accurate health knowledge will influence attitude and practice. Pregnant women with good nutritional knowledge will avoid anaemia and its attendant pregnancy complications like low birth weight babies, preterm deliveries, fatigue, shortness of breath, postpartum depression, difficult labor due to inability to push during delivery process was what informed the conduct of this empirical study.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to find out the effects of health instructions on knowledge of anaemia among women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State. Specifically, the study investigated the followings:

1. To ascertain the pretest results of the experimental and control groups on health knowledge of anaemia among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State.
2. To examine the pretest and post-test results of the experimental group on health knowledge of anaemia among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State.
3. To find out the difference between post-test results of the experimental groups after the intervention of health instructions on health knowledge of anaemia among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What was the knowledge of the pre-test of the experimental group and the control group on anaemia among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State?
2. What was the knowledge of the pretest and post-test of the experimental group on anaemia among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State?

3. What was the knowledge of the post-test of the experimental group after intervention of health instructions on anaemia among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were derived from the research questions to guide the study:

1. There will be no significant difference in health knowledge of anaemia between the pretest results of the experimental and control groups among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State.
2. There will be no significant difference in health knowledge of anaemia between the pretest and post-test results of the experimental group among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State.
3. There will be no significant difference in health knowledge of anaemia between the post-test results of the experimental groups after the intervention of health instructions and the control group among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State.

Significance of the Study

The study would be significant to health educators in the professional practice of health education discipline in so many perspectives. The principal benefit of this study to health educators is that it would provide a baseline data about the health knowledge possessed by women who have attained the ages of reproduction as well as all pregnant women concerning the causes, effects and prevention of anaemia. Furthermore, the baseline data generated in this study will be able to guide and redirect health educators in the provision of learning experiences to women of reproductive ages and pregnant women that is capable of imparting fundamental health knowledge that can influence attitudes, and inculcate skills that will facilitate positive behavioural change in health practice, especially as it concerns causes, effects and prevention of anaemia. In addition, the baseline data generated in this study would be significant to government and policy makers particularly in health ministries, department and agencies in that it can positively influence their policy formulation and provide a guide for a piece of legislation that will foster health knowledge for disease prevention and health promotion activities that will be well driven by health education discipline both at the communities and healthcare facilities in a bid to achieve significant reduction of pregnancy complications and maternal death from anaemia in Nigeria, including Delta state. Generally, the study would be significant to public health administrators and health programme planners since it tends to provide them with a guide towards considering consistent health promotion and disease prevention sensitization that will be driven by health education professionals across communities and healthcare facilities.

Scope of the Study

The study is geographically delimited to tertiary hospitals in Delta State, specifically Federal Medical Centre, Asaba, and Delta State University Teaching Hospital, Oghara. The content scope is restricted to anaemia with focus on the effects of health instruction on pregnant women's knowledge of anaemia.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design. The population comprised 715 pregnant women attending antenatal clinics at the two tertiary hospitals. Using Taro Yamane's formula at a precision level of 0.10, a sample of 88 pregnant women were selected. Data were collected using a 30-item structured questionnaire validated by experts in health education and measurement, with reliability coefficients of 0.99. The experimental group received a 4-week structured health instructions delivered through lesson plans and notes, while the control group received routine antenatal care without the structured instruction. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics to answer research questions and inferential statistics such as paired t-test, independent t-test, and ANCOVA to test hypotheses at 0.05 significance level.

PRESENTATION OF DATA AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The data collected in the study were presented in the following tables and analyzed below based on the research questions and hypotheses generated.

Table 1: Demographic Distribution of respondents

Variable	Option	Frequency	Percentage
Location	Urban	53	60.2
	Rural	35	39.8
Educational Background	Primary	24	27.25
	Secondary	40	45.5
	Tertiary	24	27.25

Table 1 presented the demographic distribution of respondents based on location and educational background. The data show that a majority of the participants 53(60.2%) resided in urban areas, while 35(39.8%) were residing in rural locations. Regarding educational background 40(45.5%) of the respondents attained secondary education. This was followed by primary education with 24(27.3%) and tertiary education being the least with 24 (27.3%). This suggested that most of the respondents had basic to moderate formal education and were more resident in urban areas.

Research Question 1: *What is the knowledge of the pre-test of the experimental group and the control group on anaemia among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State?*

Table 2: Analysis of knowledge of the pre-test of the experimental group and the control group on anaemia among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals

Group	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Control Group	49	3.16	2.80	0.65
Experimental Group	39	2.51	2.37	

Table 2 presented the analysis of the pre-test knowledge scores on anaemia among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State. The table compared the knowledge levels between the control group (FMC, Asaba) and the experimental group (DELSUTH) before any intervention was administered. According to the data, the control group consisted of 49 participants, with a mean knowledge score of 3.16 and a standard deviation of 2.80. In comparison, the experimental group had 39 participants, with a slightly lower mean score of 2.51 and a standard deviation of 2.37. The mean difference between the two groups is 0.65.

This result shown that prior to the intervention, both groups had relatively low knowledge of anaemia, with the control group demonstrating a marginally higher mean score than the experimental group. However, the difference in mean scores (0.65) is not substantial, suggesting that the two groups had fairly comparable levels of baseline knowledge on the subject. The absence of a test for statistical significance (such as a t-value or p-value) limits the ability to determine whether this observed difference is meaningful. Nonetheless, the findings indicated that both groups started from similar levels of knowledge, which provided a reasonable foundation for evaluating the impact of any educational intervention delivered to the experimental group.

Research Question 2: *What is the knowledge of the pretest and post-test of the experimental group on anaemia among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State?*

Table 3: Paired Sample t-test analysis of knowledge of the pretest and post-test of the experimental group on anaemia among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State?

Test Phase	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Post-Test	39	4.33	2.74	1.45
Pre-Test	39	2.88	2.63	

Table 3 presented a paired sample t-test analysis which compared the pre-test and post-test knowledge scores of anaemia among pregnant women in the experimental group attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State. This analysis was aimed at determining whether there was a significant improvement in the knowledge of participants after the administration of the health instructions. The data shown the experimental group had 39 participants. The mean score in the pre-test phase was 2.88 with a standard deviation of 2.63, while the post-test mean score increased to 4.33 with a standard deviation of 2.74. The mean difference between the post-test and pre-test scores was 1.45. This increase in the mean score indicated a notable improvement in the participants' knowledge of anaemia following the intervention. The difference of 1.45 suggested that the health instructions administered as intervention had a positive effect on raising awareness and understanding of anaemia among the pregnant women in the experimental group. Although the table does not provide a p-value to confirm statistical significance, the observed improvement in mean scores implies a meaningful gain in knowledge as a result of the intervention.

Research Question 3: *What is the knowledge of the post-test of the experimental group after intervention of health instructions on anaemia among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State?*

Table 4: ANCOVA Analysis of the post-test knowledge of the experimental group on anaemia among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals

N	Mean Score	Std. Deviation	Minimum Score	Maximum Score	Score Range (1–10)	Distribution Summary	Remark
39	5.95	2.22	1	10	1.00 – 10.00	Majority scored between 5 and 8	High knowledge level

Table 4 revealed that the post-test knowledge distribution of the experimental group on anaemia following the administration of the health instructions. The mean score was 5.95 (SD = 2.22), suggesting an above-average understanding of anaemia among the respondents. The frequency distribution indicated that a significant number of participants scored between 5 and 8, representing 63.9% of the total group (i.e., 25 out of 39). Very few respondents scored on the lower end (1–3), while scores of 9 and 10 were recorded by only 4 participants (10.3%), indicating that a smaller number achieved the highest knowledge levels. These results reflected a generally high level of knowledge after the intervention, indicating that the health instruction had a positive impact on the pregnant women's knowledge of anaemia. The upward shift in concentrations of scores around the mid to upper values, and low frequency of poor scores collectively demonstrated the effectiveness of the health instruction as an intervention for improvement of the knowledge of anaemia capable of reducing its associated pregnancy complications and maternal mortality among women.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

There will be no significant difference in health knowledge of anaemia between the pretest results of the experimental and control groups among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State.

Table 5: T-Test Analysis of the Difference in Pretest Health Knowledge of Anaemia Between Experimental and Control Groups

Group	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Diff	t-value	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remark
Experimental Group	39	2.6154	2.41285	0.0236	0.043	86	0.966	Not statistically significant
Control Group	49	2.5918	2.62931					

Table 5 presented the results of an independent samples t-test conducted to test the hypothesis that there will be no significant difference in the pretest of health knowledge of anaemia between the experimental group (DELSUTH, Oghara) and the control group (FMC, Asaba). The experimental group had a mean score of 2.62, while the control group had a mean score of 2.59, showing a negligible mean difference of 0.0236. The t-test result yielded a t-value of 0.043 and a p-value of 0.966, which is far above the 0.05 threshold for statistical significance. The 95% confidence interval for the difference (-1.058 to 1.105) included zero. This further confirmed the observed difference which may be likely due to chance. Thus, the result supported the null hypothesis that there was no significant difference in the pretest knowledge of anaemia between the two groups before the intervention. The result suggested that both groups began the study with similar level of baseline knowledge of anaemia, making them suitable for evaluation of the effect of the health instruction intervention.

Hypothesis 2

There will be no significant difference in health knowledge of anaemia between the pretest and post-test results of the experimental group among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State.

Table 6: T-Test Analysis of Pretest and Post-Test Health Knowledge of Anaemia in Experimental and Control Groups

Test Phase	Group	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Diff	t-value	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remark
Experimental Group	Pretest	39	2.51	2.37					Higher post-intervention gain and Statistically significant
	Post-test	39	5.95	2.22	3.44	5.80	86	0.000	

Table 9 presented the t-test analysis that compared the pretest and post-test scores of health knowledge of anaemia for the experimental group among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State. The pretest mean score for the experimental group (n = 39) was 2.51 (SD = 2.37), while the post-test mean score increased to 5.95 (SD = 2.22), yielding a mean difference of 3.44. The calculated t-value of 5.80 at df = 86 with a p-value of 0.000 (p < 0.05) indicated that the observed difference was statistically significant. The p-value was less than 0.05 hence the null hypothesis which stated that there would be no significant difference between the pretest and post-test health knowledge scores was rejected. This means that the administration of the health instructions as intervention significantly improved the health knowledge of anaemia among pregnant women in the experimental group.

Hypothesis 3

There will be no significant difference in health knowledge of anaemia between the post-test results of the experimental groups and the control group among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in tertiary hospitals in Delta State.

Table 7: ANCOVA Analysis of Post-Test Health Knowledge on Anaemia Between Experimental and Control Groups

Variable	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F-value	Sig. (p-value)	Partial Eta Squared	Remark
Post Anemia	Experimental Group	39	5.95	2.22	15.154	.000	.291	Statistically significant
	Control Group	49	3.04	2.42				

Table 6 presented the ANCOVA result that examined the effect of health instructions on post-test knowledge of anaemia by comparing the experimental group (DELSUTH) and the control group (FMC Asaba), while controlling for pre-test scores. The experimental group had a mean post-test score of 5.95, whereas the control group had a lower post-test mean of 3.04. The analysis revealed a statistically significant difference between the two groups, with an F-value of 15.154 and a p-value of .000, which was less than the 0.05 significance level. The partial eta squared of 0.291 indicated a moderate to large effect size, suggesting that the health instruction intervention had a meaningful impact on participants’ knowledge of anaemia. Since the p-value was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means there was a significant difference in the post-test knowledge of anaemia between the experimental group (who received the health instruction) and the control group. The health instruction was found effective in improvement of health knowledge of anaemia among the experimental group.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study demonstrated that pregnant women in both the experimental and control groups initially had poor knowledge of anaemia as shown by the pre-test results. This confirmed the researcher’s expectation that ignorance and misconceptions about anaemia being one of the pregnancy-related ailments is widespread among women attending antenatal clinics. The similarity in baseline scores further validated the quasi-experimental design, ensuring that any post-intervention changes were attributable to the health instructions. This was consistent with Appiah et al. (2020) reports of low maternal knowledge of anaemia among pregnant women in Ghana. Following the intervention, the study revealed a statistically significant improvement in the knowledge of anaemia among women in the experimental group in line with the outcome of a similar quasi-experimental study of Elsharkawy et al (2022) that group of persons administered with an intervention tagged Health Information Package Programme (HIPP) attain significant increase in the mean knowledge scores, food selection ability scores and improvement in their haemoglobin levels after three (3) months of the HIPP intervention to improve knowledge of anaemia among pregnant women. The findings also tallied with the recommendation of the study by Suryanarayana et al (2017) that structured health education would be effective in reducing ignorance and improve adherence to preventive measures like iron-rich diets and supplementation. The improvement in the experimental group over the control group further confirmed the potency of health instruction in bridging knowledge gaps of anaemia among pregnant women.

In summary, the discussion of findings established that health instruction had a significant and positive effect on the knowledge of anaemia among pregnant women in Delta State. The consistency of these results with both local and international studies confirmed that health instruction is a reliable intervention for addressing maternal ignorance about anaemia, improving pregnancy outcomes, and ultimately reducing maternal and neonatal mortality.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that structured health instruction is an effective intervention for improving knowledge of anaemia among pregnant women since it has shown strong potency for prevention of anaemic condition during pregnancy thereby reducing maternal and child mortalities as well as contributing to the achievement of sustainable maternal health in Delta State, and indeed Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Health instruction on anaemia should be made an integral part of antenatal care in all tertiary hospitals in Delta State and policies and laws should be enacted to reposition health education discipline to take charge of this task across health facilities
2. Nurses and midwives should work with professionally trained health educators to deliver effective and structured health instruction sessions during antenatal visits to healthcare facilities.
3. Pregnant women should be encouraged to participate actively in antenatal classes where pregnancy-related health issues are taught especially on topic like anaemia
4. Further research should be conducted on other pregnancy-related ailments to broaden the scope of health instruction interventions.

REFERENCES

- Abu-Ouf, N.M. and John, M. M. (2015) The impacts of maternal iron deficiency anemia on child health. *Saudi Med J.* 36 (2):145-149
- Appiah, P. K., Nkuah, D. and Bonchel, D. A. (2020) Knowledge and adherence to anaemia prevention strategies among pregnant women attending antenatal care facilities in Juaboso District in western-north region, Ghana *Journal of pregnancy* <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/2139892> Retrieved 05/7/2023.
- Asrie, F. (2017) Prevalence of anaemia and its associated factors among pregnant women receiving antenatal care at Aymiba Health center, North-West, *Journal of Blood Medicine* 8 (1): 35-40. www.hindawi.com Retrieved 12/1/2023.
- Elsharkawy, N. B., Abdelaziz, E. M., Ouda, M. M. and Oraby, F. A. (2022) Effectiveness of health information package and compliance among pregnant women with anaemia: Randomized control trial, Saudi-Arabia: *Int. J Environ Res Public Health* 2022, (19) 5: 2724; <http://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19052724>
- Ilo, C. (2017) What is the difference between health instruction and health education www.quora.com Retrieved 24/8/2024.
- Kadry, S., Sleem, G. and Samad, R. A. (2018) Haemoglobin Levels in pregnant women and its outcomes. *Biom biostat int. Journal* 7(4): 326 – 336.
- Koyuncu, K, Turgay, Y, Sukur, E, Yildirim, B, Ates, C. and Soylemez, F (2017) Third Trimester Anemia extends the length of hospital stay after delivery. *Journal of Turkish society of obstetric and gynecology* 14(3): 166 – 169.
- Omote, V, Ukwamedua, H.A., Bini, N., Kashibu, E., Ubardoma, J.R. and Ranyang, A. (2020) prevalence, severity and correlates of anemia in pregnancy among antenatal attended in Warri, South-southern Nigeria. *National library of medicine - PMC pub Med PMID: 32455008*
- Onoh, R., Lawani, O., Ezeonu, P., Nkwo, P., Omoh, T. J. and Ajah, L. (2015) Predictors of Anaemia in pregnant woman accessing antenatal care in poor resource settings in South Eastern Nigeria. *Sahel Medical Journal* 18 (4): 182 – 187. www.hindawi.com Retrieved 12/01/2023.
- Robinson, K. (2023) Difference between health education and health instruction. www.quora.com Retrieved 25/8/2024.
- Suryanarayana, R, Chandrappa, M, Santhuran, A. N., Prathima, S. and Sheela, S. R (2017) Prospective study on prevalence of anemia of pregnant women and its outcome: a community based study *J. family med prim care* 6(4): 739-743 doi: 104103/jfmpc.jfmpc 3317 PMID: PMC5848390 Retrieved 8/7/2023
- UNICEF (2023) Saving mothers before, during and after childbirth: Life savings innovative approaches addressing maternal mortalities globally. A UN report trends in maternal mortality 2000-2020. www.unicef.org retrieved 13/09/25
- WHO (2023) *Anaemia overview* www.who.int accessed 29/01/2023